

Artificial Intelligence and Educational Management: Ethical and Philosophical Perspectives in Teaching and Learning

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Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into educational management is rapidly reshaping teaching, learning, assessment and administrative processes. While AI promises efficiency, personalization, and data-driven insights, it also raises profound ethical and philosophical identity and the purpose of education. This paper explores: (1) how AI is being used in educational management and pedagogy, (2) Core ethical challenges and philosophical tensions arising from AI integration and (3) Recommendations for educational managers to adopt AI responsibility in teaching and learning. Drawing on recent empirical studies and theoretical work, the article argues that educational leaders must align the use of AI with core educational values, human flourishing justice, autonomy and establish governance professional development and policy framework to guide ethical AI practice.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Educational Management, Ethics, Philosophy, Teaching and Learning.

Introduction

Educational Management traditionally involves oversight of curriculum, staff resources student outcomes, and institutional policy. In recent years, the rise of Artificial Intelligent (AI) technologies such as intelligent tutoring systems, predictive analytics, automated assessment tools and generative AI has opened new possibilities for educational management and pedagogy (Smith,2021) These innovations however challenge fundamental questions such as what is the roles of the teacher when AI can generate content? How should we value human-student relationships when AI systems personalize learning paths? What obligations exist to ensure fairness, transparency, privacy and professional autonomy? For educational administrators and leaders, managing AI means more than installing tools, it means stewarding ethical and philosophical commitments in a rapidly evolving landscape. AI is reshaping how we teach, learn and manage educational institutions. These advancements compel us to ask questions like what values are embedded in these systems? Who benefits, and who might be left behind? (Holmes et al., 2019; Baroody & Wilkin-Yel, 2021).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Educational Management:

In education, artificial intelligence (AI) is changing educational management, teaching and learning process. Recent studies have revealed AI's potential to personalize learning, optimize administrative task, and foster student engagement. Educational management systems are progressively incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) to help data driven decision-making, personalize learning and increase administrative efficiently AI-powered platforms adapt content to individual student needs, learning pace and preferences. Virtual tutors provide real-time

feedback and support, improving student engagement. AI tools generate quizzes, summarize texts and automate grading, saving time for teachers. AI analyzes student behaviour and performance to inform instructional strategies (Smith, 2022; Teixeira et al.,2021)

Creely and Caraboth (2025) hinted that AI reconfigures roles and relationships such as teachers as facilitators, and AI as co-agent, and therefore, must accompany ethical and pedagogical reflection. In addition, Reiss (2021) notes that while AI offers personalization, it also risk reducing the social relational dimension of education, unless managed carefully.

AI technologies are applied in institutional settings to automate activities including grading, admission processing, curriculum design and scheduling, hence reducing the administrative load on administrators and educators (Luckin et al., 2016; Teixeira et al.,2021)

In addition, to promoting differentiated learning routes, AI-powered learning management systems (LMS) can tailor instructional material dependence on student needs. Early identification of at-risk students, better resource allocation, and improved institutional performance monitoring result from predictive analytics for school administrators (Holmes, et al., 2023; Smith, 2021). These features help educational administrators to simplify processes and give instructional leadership and strategic planning top priority.

The incorporation of artificial intelligence in education management, however also introduces fresh difficulties in accountability and governance. Although artificial intelligence gives operational efficiency. It demands a lot of human supervision to guarantee that technical interventions fit educational ideals and objectives. AI systems raising system biases, marginalizing educators' expertise, or fostering dependency on automated decision-making are major challenges in an AI-driven education system (Peters & Bassey, 2020).

Similarly, Selwyn (2020) warns that if not carefully controlled, artificial intelligence might depersonalize education, thereby transforming teaching and learning into merely transactional processes rather than inclusive human experiences. Recognizing that education is a profoundly human endeavor to be cultivated, rather than simply a system to be optimized. Educational managements therefore must not only embrace artificial intelligence with technical competence but also with ethical awareness and philosophical insight (Igbokwe,2023).

Artificial Intelligence Technology and Ethical Perspectives in Teaching and Learning

The growing use of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning has presented a range of ethical problems particularly in the areas of data privacy, informed consent, algorithmic fairness and bias, autonomy and human agency in learning, transparency and explain- ability in AI systems, the authenticity of AI assisted work and equity in access to AI enhanced education (Karpouzis, 2024). Peters and Bassey (2020) explained that, AI powered- educational management may negatively affect human interactions and personalization which can lead to poor student achievement.

Data privacy and security is another major ethical challenge in AI driven education. Data privacy involves ensuring that individuals' personal and sensitive information such as names, academic records, learning patterns or biometric data is handled responsibly and ethically. On the other hand, data security refers to the technical and administrative measures taken to protect data from unauthorized access, theft, loss or misuse. AI relies heavily on large data sets and if misused or breached, it can lead to identity theft, student profiling or biased decision-making (Prinsloo & Slade, 2017; Hills et al.,2020). Regan and Jesse (2019) observed that the success of AI systems in individualizing learning experience and insight to student performance depends mainly on the collection and analysis of large number of student data. Prinsloo and Slade (2017) hinted that the collection of large size of data can lead to significant privacy challenge especially when the data

has to do with minors that may not fully understand the impact of their data being collected and analyzed. Educational managers should be able to promote a culture of responsibility, transparency and trust in how data is collected and used. Karakas and Yuce (2025) advocated for AI literacy frameworks that integrate technological skill with ethical considerations.

Educational administrators need to invest on the professional development of staff so that, teachers and other members of staff can undergo training in ethical use of AI, understanding its limitations and integrating it pedagogically and philosophically. Alnsour et al. (2025) explored how university of Jordan academic staff perceive AI ethics. They found gaps in awareness and institutional support especially around tools like ChatGPT and automated grading systems.

In an AI-driven educational management system, balancing AI support and learner autonomy, and enhancing human agency is very crucial. Learners' autonomy involves their ability to control their learning process making choices and decisions about what, how and when they learn, while human agency involves learners' capacity to act intentionally, making decisions and taking actions that shape their learning experiences. Selwyn (2020) vividly acknowledge the fact that, though personalized learning powered by AI can adapt to individual student needs, there is also the challenge of over reliance on algorithmic recommendations by students and this can limit their ability to explore different kinds of subjects, develop critical thinking skills and take intellectual risk. The increasing use of AI in the teaching and learning process can also negatively impact the development of students' emotional and social skills (Karpouzis, 2024) and furthermore, Aoun (2017) elucidated that, as AI takes on more functions in the teaching and learning process, there is the risk of diminishing the vital human elements of education. In order to reduce the influence of AI on learners' autonomy and enhancing human agency, educational managers must ensure that AI systems promote, rather than undermine learners' autonomy and agency (Igbokwe,2023). AI can provide support but learners must retain control over their learning paths and decisions (Selwyn,2020)

Algorithmic fairness and bias are major ethical issue in AI-driven education, and they describe how artificial intelligence (AI) systems used in teaching and learning treat students equitably without showing favour or bias to any individual or group based on race, gender, socio-economic status, language, and learning ability (Wilkins-Yel, 2021). Biases in AI systems increase or aggravate existing imbalances in education leading to the detriment of students from minority groups or low-income background. AI-driven systems can make suppositions about learners' abilities and potentials based on demographic information, impeding students' educational opportunities (Kizilcec & Lee, 2022; Zhou et al.,2022). Educational managers need to ensure that AI tools are audited, inclusive and used with human oversight to prevent harm and promote fairness.

The authenticity of AI assisted work is another area that raises ethical eye-brows in AI driven education. The authenticity of AI assisted work shows how genuine, original and truthful the output is when a person uses AI tools such ChatGPT or other writing /generation tools in creating academic or profession work. When AI is used ethically, it maintains academic honesty, protects intellectual property right and ensures trust in the work's quality and source (Smith, 2022). AI tools are becoming more sophisticated in generating text, and solving problems, however, there are questions about the limits of their acceptable use in educational management systems. Educational administrators play a critical role in ensuring the authenticity of AI – assisted work within their institutions. They help set clear expectations, policies and ethical standards for how AI is used by students, teachers and other staff.

Transparency and explain-ability are major ethical challenges in AI driven education. This is because they deal with how clearly decisions and operations of AI systems can be understood by users especially students, teachers, and educational managers. Transparency in AI-powered education simply refers to how openly and clearly an AI system reveals what data it uses; how it makes decisions such as grading, and predictions, and who controls the system.

AI tools are like black boxes and their internal logic is hidden making it hard to know how and why a decision was made. A good example is when an AI grading tool gives a student a low score, but neither the teacher nor the student understands why. The ethical question here is who is responsible if the AI makes a harmful or unfair decision? Lack of explanation many hide bias or discrimination. (Rudin, 2019). Teachers and students may find it difficult to trust or accept AI-driven results, if they cannot understand them, hence, AI users need to know how their data is used to make decision. Accountability, fairness, trust, and informed consent are core ethical elements of transparency and AI in education can become unfair, unacceptable and harmful to learning integrity without transparency and explain- ability. Ryan (2020) however, argued that while AI meets all of the requirement of the rational account of trust, it will be shown that this is not actually a type of trust at all, but is instead a form of reliance. Furthermore, he argued that ultimately, even complex machines such as AI should not be viewed as trustworthy as this undermines the value of interpersonal trust. Many AI algorithms, most especially those using deep learning techniques, operate as “black boxes”, making decisions or recommendations in ways that are difficult to be interpreted by humans. AI can also shift focus from deep understanding to data driven outcome (Rudin, 2019). Educational administrators should ensure that, AI encourages critical thinking and meaningful learning. Artificial intelligence (AI) challenges traditional notions of knowledge and learning requiring new epistemological framework (Selwyn 2020). Farooqi et al. (2024) emphasized the need for extensive training of teachers to support enabling the integration of AI.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Technology in Learning and teaching: Philosophical Perspectives

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into teaching and learning situations has raised some significant philosophical questions on the nature, purpose and ethics of education. It also challenged the traditional philosophical foundations such as the human role in knowledge creation, the definition of learning, and the values of education (Williamson & Piattoeva 2018). The epistemological perspective of philosophy of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning environment emphasizes the questions what count as knowledge when machines can generate, curate and even teach it? How do learners construct meaning when AI systems curate or generate content? Who holds epistemic authority -teachers, learners or algorithms? It focuses on how AI influences the way knowledge is acquired, validated and interpreted. There are concerns however among educators and other AI users on the use of AI. Some of these concerns are:

The use of AI tools such as ChatGPT challenge conventional perception of knowledge authority, with learners steadily depending on AI generated content. With AI automating tasks, teachers risk losing autonomy and becoming overseers of machine-led workflows. Kucukuncular and Ertugan (2025) warns of alienation and the need for teacher empowerment.

AI encouraging surface learning such as getting quick answers through chatbots instead of profound comprehension. Chaparro-Banegas et al. (2024) suggests that, AI tools can complement critical thinking as long as governments and economic agents direct their use toward ethical and transparent purposes.

The ontological perspective of philosophy on artificial intelligence in teaching and learning focuses on the evolving role of the teacher and learner in AI-driven environments. It emphasizes

the question what does it mean to be a teacher or a learner when artificial intelligence (AI) can replicate instruction roles? There has been a great concern on over-reliance on artificial intelligence (AI) which can lead to depersonalizing leaning and shift human connection and identity in education (Williamson & Piattoeva 2018).

With AI tools providing content, feedback and personalization, the traditional roles of teachers may shift and cause them to be facilitators or co-learners. Secondly, many learners may not have the privilege to be engaged with human mentors but with algorithmic agents. Knowledge also can be less static content from teacher to student but more dynamic, co-created, and mediated by AI system. Creely and Caraboth (2025) in their study on teaching and learning with AI; An integrated AI-oriented pedagogical model' discussed how teachers' positionality shifted from authoritative knowledge holders to facilitators, sand how teachers' relationality reframes AI as co-creative presence under AI integration. In addition, Kamali et al. (2024) revealed that, many teachers lack awareness of artificial intelligence, ethical frameworks and therefore struggle with alignment between personal and institutional values.

The axiological perspective of philosophy in AI powered education focuses on the purpose of education beyond human dignity, creativity, and empathy. The growing reliance on AI for instruction and decision-making raises concerns about autonomy accountability and human agency in the learning process. It is believed that AI may prioritize outcomes like test scores over holistic development. Holmes et al. (2023) argued for designing AI to align with the values of equity and inclusion. Similarly, Williamson and Piattoeva (2018) hinted that AI is redefining what count as teacher' learner', and learning'. Educational administrators therefore should not only focus on the technological efficiency of artificial intelligence (AI) but also address its philosophical implications to ensure that the use of AI aligns with the holistic and ethical goals of education.

Implication of AI -Powered Teaching and Learning to Educational Managers

Educational managers need to know that adopting AI-driven education changes who learns and how. They must lead with an awareness of the ontological shifts and not just efficiency gains. They should ensure that AI integration support human flourishing, agency and meaningful relationality rather reaching humans to data inputs in AI systems Policies and professional development should address what it means to teach and learn in an AI-rich context renewing the ontology of educator and learner. They should engage stakeholders like the teachers, students, and the community in reflecting on changes in roles relationships, identity and purpose brought by artificial intelligence. Igbokwe (2023) warns that AI has enormous capacity to enhance educational management, however, it must be adopted with caution. In addition, Chen (2025) advocated for AI integration that aligns with core educational values and maintain human epistemic agency.

Conclusion

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into teaching and learning process presents not just technical changes, but deep ethical and philosophical shifts that educational administrator must address with wisdom and intentionality. While AI promotes efficiency, personalization, and access to learning, it also raises questions about fairness, transparency, human agency, data privacy, and the meaning of education itself.

From a philosophical perspective, AI challenges traditional views of teaching and learning- redefining the roles of teachers and students altering the nature of knowledge transmission, and potentially shifting educational values from human development to technological optimization. Ontologically, AI changes what it means to 'be' a learner or educator; ethically, it demands careful scrutiny of bias, accountability and inclusion.

Therefore, educational management should go beyond adoption and functionality. They must ensure AI is aligned with human centered educational goals, supports ethical practices, protects learner identity and rights, and preserves the relational and transformations core of education. In doing so, AI becomes not just a tool for innovation but a partner in cultivating a more just, meaningful, and inclusive learning future.

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